

Robustifying cooperative awareness in autonomous vehicles through local information diffusion

Nikos Piperigkos^{1,2}, Aris S. Lalos², Kostas Berberidis^{1,2}

¹Computer Engineering and Informatics Dept., University of Patras, Greece

²Industrial Systems Institute, Athena Research Center, Patras Science Park, Greece

Emails: piperigkos@ceid.upatras.gr, lalos@isi.gr, berberid@ceid.upatras.gr

Abstract—Cooperative Intelligent Transportation Systems envision the integration of cooperative intelligence as a key operational part of autonomous driving. In this way, a fleet or swarm of Connected and Automated Vehicles collectively coordinates its driving actions in order to maximize its performance. To realize this ambition, vehicles need to be fully location-aware of their surrounding environment, through distributed AI intelligence. Motivated by this requirement, we develop in this paper a distributed cooperative awareness scheme which performs multimodal fusion of heterogeneous sensor sources along with V2V communication information, using graph Laplacian matrix and Least-Mean-Squares algorithm. The intuition behind our approach is that neighboring vehicles are interested in estimating common positions of other vehicles. We build upon our previous work on global awareness through local information diffusion, and prove that the proposed distributed framework is able to address highly efficient the case of lacking any information about other networked vehicles. More specifically, our approach achieves high enough convergence speed as well as location accuracy. The evaluation study has been performed in CARLA autonomous driving simulator and verifies the proposed method’s benefits over other related solutions.

Index Terms—Localization, Cooperative Awareness, Least-Mean-Squares, Information diffusion, Sensor fusion

I. INTRODUCTION

The entrance of Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) in public and urban roads features the great potential of reducing traffic accidents and air pollution, improving the safety and comfort of driver and passengers, minimizing energy consumption, etc. To optimize their driving performance, vehicles need to proactively monitor not only their own state but also those of the nearby road users, formulating a swarm of intelligent nodes which focus on collectively achieving challenging driving tasks. Vehicle-to-Vehicle and Everything (V2V-V2X) communications facilitate this type of coordination, through the edge cloud computing [1]. In this regard, the three-levels swarm concept can be adopted: on-board computation; computation at the edge; and finally, resource richer multicloud computing environments. Location or cooperative awareness (CA) [2], in which the vehicles constantly broadcast messages including position, speed, heading, etc., is a task of major significance. Localization module serves as the mediator between perception and path planning [3], providing location

information to the vehicles. However, stand-alone solutions relying on either Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) or camera and LIDAR based odometry suffer from high measurement noise and drift. This work aims to collaborating multimodal sensor fusion coupled with V2V information in order to improve CA ability of involved vehicles.

Cooperative Localization (CL) is a well studied topic. For example, studies [4], [5] provide an overview of different CL approaches, discussing the two main distinctive points: processing architecture (centralized or distributed) and estimation algorithm (optimization or Bayesian based). Centralized architectures serve as the theoretical baseline, while distributed are more cost effective due to scalability in adaptive topologies, lower communication and computational resources, etc. Optimization based methods aim to define and minimize in a few steps a target cost function, while Bayesian or tracking address the CL task as a probabilistic inference problem. Centralized optimization based method of [6], extends the traditional trilateration scheme with relative velocity measurements, assuming nodes with and without location information. Distributed Kalman filtering (KF) has been employed in [7] so as to the ego vehicle improve its location information. To do so, it exploits a set of global and local filters comprised of self and relative measurements to other vehicles, which are then optimally fused. The authors of [8] introduced a unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) based assistance system, for enhancing the quality of position measurement of road users. To do so, they proposed the Bayesian framework of non-parametric belief propagation, which in turn requires very high number of particles. Global awareness of CAVs based on distributed information diffusion has been introduced in [9], with very promising results of location accuracy. The requirement for all-to-all V2V communication at the initialization stage is a limitation that should be addressed. Covariance intersection (CI) has been employed in the CA scenario of a multi-robot group in [10]. Each robot makes use of an Extended KF (EKF), exploiting relative observations to landmarks and other robots. Although CI ensured communication resilience and estimation consistency, the evaluation has been performed in a rather undynamic indoor environment, with fixed communication topologies.

To further boost the performance of CA we propose a local diffusion based approach, which addresses the limitations

This paper was supported by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI) under the 3rd Call for HFRI PhD Fellowships (Fellowship Number: 6372) and the EU’s H2020 research and innovation programme CPSoSaware under grant agreement No 871738.

of global awareness solution related to lacking knowledge about other networked vehicles and convergence speed. The proposed framework is linear with respect to its parameters (instead of [10] and [11]), totally distributed, and doesn't depend on fixed communication topologies.

The main contributions could be summarized as follows:

- A local diffusion based awareness scheme is proposed, in which every vehicle estimates its own target location vector. Least-Mean-Squares (LMS) algorithm has been used for the distributed solution of target cost function.
- Local graph Laplacian matrix was employed for the derivation of a linear measurement model comprised of multimodal measurement sources.
- The solution doesn't depend on fixed vehicular topologies, but rather addresses dynamic and sparse topologies, without all-to-all V2V communication.
- Realistic simulations carried out in CARLA simulator [12], verify the proposed analysis as well as its benefits.

Outline: Section II presents the system model and the problem formulation; Section III reviews global awareness framework; Section IV formulates the novel local information diffusion based scheme and derives the solution; Section V is dedicated to numerical results and evaluation, while Section VI concludes this work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

This Section introduces the general system model of cooperative localization and awareness task for a fleet of CAVs.

A. Preliminaries

As illustrated in Fig. 1, CAVs of the traffic network are equipped with sensors including monocular, stereo or fish-eye cameras, LIDAR, GNSS, IMU, etc., in order to be aware of their surrounding environment. To do so, scene analysis

Fig. 1. Traffic network

and understanding, i.e., visually detect nearby objects (e.g., vehicles, cyclists, pedestrians) by drawing bounding boxes, are necessary pre-processing steps. Deep learning can be considered paramount for this challenging perception task [13]. Localization is a step beyond perception, since it is required for optimizing the driving performance of vehicle through advanced path planning and control.

Ground truth 2D position of vehicle i at time instant t is represented by vector $\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} = [x^{(t)} \ y^{(t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$. At the same time, various measurements of self positioning as well as relative observations are available for utilization by vehicle i .

Self positioning provides noisy estimations of location though visual odometry [14], LIDAR odometry [15], GNSS/IMU fusion, etc. This requires the different solutions to correspond to the same reference system, so as to be aligned between them. Relative observations can be considered the distance and azimuth angle between an observing vehicle and its neighbor, using the 3D centroids of detected bounding boxes by LIDAR sensor. To be more specific, multimodal measurements (both self and relative) available to i are defined below:

- Self positioning:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(t)} = \mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} + \mathbf{n}_{p,i}^{(t)}, \quad \mathbf{n}_{p,i}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \Sigma_p) \quad (1)$$

- Relative observation:

$$\tilde{z}_{o,ij}^{(t)} = h_o(\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}) + n_{o,ij}^{(t)}, \quad n_{o,ij}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \sigma_o^2) \quad (2)$$

When relative o-bservation refers to d-istance, then $h_d(\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}) = \|\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} - \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}\|$ and $\sigma_o^2 = \sigma_d^2$, while with az-imuth angle $h_{az}(\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}) = \phi_{ij}^{(t)} - \theta_i^{(t)}$,

$$\phi_{ij}^{(t)} = \begin{cases} \lambda\pi + \arctan \frac{|x_j^{(t)} - x_i^{(t)}|}{|y_j^{(t)} - y_i^{(t)}|}, & \lambda = 0, 1 \\ \lambda\pi + \arctan \frac{|y_j^{(t)} - y_i^{(t)}|}{|x_j^{(t)} - x_i^{(t)}|}, & \lambda = \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2} \end{cases} \quad \text{and (truncated}$$

to $[0, 2\pi]$) $\sigma_o^2 = \sigma_{az}^2$. Azimuth angle is shown in Fig. 2, with yaw angle $\theta_i^{(t)}$ of vehicle i . In addition, the relative

Fig. 2. Relative observations

observation of differential coordinate $h_{dc}(\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}) = \delta_i^{(t)}$ is defined accordingly: $\delta_i^{(t)} = [\delta_i^{(x,t)} \ \delta_i^{(y,t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$, with $\delta_i^{(x,t)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} -\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)} \sin \tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)}$ and $\delta_i^{(y,t)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} -\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)}$. Note that $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$ is the neighborhood of i . Measurement noise is assumed to be Gaussian and mutually independent over the vehicles of the network [8].

Vehicle i in order to optimally plan its future driving actions and maximize its safety and efficiency, has to be location-aware of its surrounding connected neighbors. As a matter of fact, i aims to estimate both its own as well the others' vehicles positions in a distributed manner. To be more detailed, two cases can be identified: i) global awareness, in which the state $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$ of i comprises of the 2D locations of all vehicles belonging to the same traffic network or cluster $\mathcal{C}^{(t)}$, and ii) local awareness, in which the state $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$ comprises of the 2D locations of vehicles belonging to the 1-hop and direct neighborhood $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$ of i . Note that in all cases, the target state is to be estimated in a distributed manner.

Communication range r_c identifies the V2V links between the CAVs, in a way that if visually measured $\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)} > r_c$ then i doesn't consider j as a connected neighbor.

B. Problem formulation

Consider the graph $\mathcal{C}^{(t)}$ of Fig. 3, depicting a cluster of CAVs. Nodes represent the vehicles, while edges imply V2V communications links and availability of relative observations. Denote $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)} = \text{col}\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_1^{(t)}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2^{(t)}, \dots\}$ as the col-

Fig. 3. Example graph of traffic network and corresponding star graph

lection of the individual target location vectors of vehicles. Each vehicle is associated with a twice differentiable and strongly convex risk function $\mathcal{J}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}; \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)})$, conditioned over the available measurement vector $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}$ to i . The general form of $\mathcal{J}(\cdot)$ is that of a squared affine function between the unknown locations and measurements, through a modelling matrix $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)}$, i.e., $\|\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}\|^2$. Additionally, we impose the smoothness of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)}$ over the underlying graph as a prior belief or regularization term. The smoothness $\mathcal{S}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)})$ as pointed out in [16] can be defined accordingly: $\mathcal{S}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)}) = \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} \mathcal{P}_{\Omega_{il}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_l^{(t)})$. Projection operator $\mathcal{P}_{\Omega_{il}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_l^{(t)})$ is equal to $\mathcal{P}_{\Omega_{il}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_l^{(t)}) = \mathbf{a}_{il} \odot \|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_l^{(t)}\|$, where \odot is the Hadamard product.

We denote $\mathcal{N}_{ij}^{(t)}$ as the set of vehicles connected to i that are also involved in estimating the location of j . To effectively fuse those overlapping estimations, i exploits a set of combination weights [17] $\mathbf{a}_{il} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{N}_{ij}^{(t)}|}$:

$$a_{il}^j = 0 \text{ if } l \notin \mathcal{N}_{ij}^{(t)}, \quad \sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}_{ij}^{(t)}} a_{il}^j = 1 \text{ and } \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}_{ij}^{(t)}} a_{il}^j = 1 \quad (3)$$

The definition of smoothness states that the smaller $\mathcal{S}(\cdot)$ is, the smoother the signal $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)}$ over the graph is. The intuition behind this statement is that $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)}$ is smooth as long as vehicles with larger a_{il}^j have many overlapping entries of their target vectors. Therefore, the goal is to minimize in a distributed manner the following convex cost function [16]:

$$\underset{\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)}}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|} \mathcal{J}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}; \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} \mathcal{P}_{\Omega_{il}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_l^{(t)}) \quad (4)$$

where vehicle i is interested in estimating the i -th sub-vector of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)}$ corresponding to $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}$, and tuning parameter $\lambda > 0$. The following Section presents in short the alternative framework

of global awareness through information diffusion in order to highlight its limitations over the proposed solution.

III. GLOBAL AWARENESS THROUGH INFORMATION DIFFUSION

Normalized Laplacian matrix $\mathbf{L}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}| \times |\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$ of the graph $\mathcal{C}^{(t)}$ is equal to $\mathbf{L}^{(t)} = \mathbf{D}^{(t)} - \mathbf{A}^{(t)}$, with $\mathbf{D}^{(t)}, \mathbf{A}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}| \times |\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$ the degree and adjacency matrices of the graph. It is proven [9] that by collecting the individual $\delta_i^{(t)}$ and putting them to vector $\tilde{\delta}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$, the locations $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$ of cluster's vehicles follow the linear system of: $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}^{(t)} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{L}^{(t)} \end{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)} = \tilde{\delta}^{(t)}$. Due to the non-singularity of $\mathbf{L}^{(t)}$, the latter is extended by the identity matrix $\mathbb{I}_{|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$, i.e., $\tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}^{(t)} \\ \mathbb{I}_{|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|} \end{bmatrix}$ while $\tilde{\delta}^{(t)}$ is enriched with the so-called anchor points $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_p^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$, i.e., the noisy self positioning measurements of the cluster, in the form of $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\delta}^{(t)T} & \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_p^{(t)T} \end{bmatrix}^T$. As a matter of fact, the previous linear system transforms to:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \end{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)} = \tilde{\mathbf{b}}^{(t)} \quad (5)$$

Global awareness through information diffusion aims to solve the centralized problem of (5) in a distributed manner. To do so, each one of the vehicles of the cluster share the common target vector $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}$. That means that each vehicle estimates the same parameter vector, i.e., the locations of all vehicles of cluster. **GLLMS** has been proposed [9] as a solution of estimating $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}$, using graph Laplacian matrix and LMS. Defining matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}_{i:}^{(t)} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{L}_{i:}^{(t)} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$, with $\mathbf{L}_{i:}^{(t)}$ the i -th row of Laplacian matrix, **GLLMS** performs two key-steps for a total number of iterations K :

$$\psi_i^{(t,k+1)} = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k)} - \mu_{1,i}^{(t)} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)T} \left(\delta_i^{(t)} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k)} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k+1)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} c_{ij}^{(t)} \psi_j^{(t,k+1)} \quad (7)$$

At each time instant and for iteration $k+1$, vehicles broadcast and receive the estimations of the common parameter from their neighbors. Each vehicle produces an intermediate estimation using (6), and updates it in (7) combining the intermediate estimations transmitted by its neighbors. Combination weights sum up to 1, i.e., $\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} c_{ij}^{(t)} = 1$. At the end of this iterative procedure, individual $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k+1)}$ shall converge to the target $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)}$.

During the first iteration, $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,0)}$ is initialized to noisy self positioning measurements of the cluster. However, unless all-to-all V2V connection or multi-hop communication has been established, vehicles are not aware of their multi-hop neighbors' positions. Parameter p indicates this rate of unknown vehicles with respect to $|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|$. In the case of Fig. 3, node 2 isn't aware of nodes 1, 5, 7 and 9, and lacks any information about them. Thus, if node 3 takes into account the

estimations from 2 then **GLLMS** will produce very inaccurate results. Although custom-made weights could address these issues, no convergence to the global solution is guaranteed. Therefore, the next Section aims to overcome these limitations by addressing the global awareness with missing entries in the following way: instead of a common across the vehicles target vector, each individual vehicle estimates its own target vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}$ with entries which overlap between neighbors.

IV. LOCAL INFORMATION DIFFUSION BASED AWARENESS

In this Section, a local diffusion based scheme for improved CA will be formulated, in which every vehicle learns or estimates the individual target vector after K iterations or transmissions among neighboring vehicles. It is based on the local Laplacian matrix and LMS algorithm. The latter algorithm can be considered a standard approach for addressing convex functions like (4), as well as when no training dataset is needed beforehand. The main motive behind our approach was the fact that for the CA task neighboring vehicles are actually estimating common locations. In this regard, each vehicle can combine and fuse those common estimations of its neighborhood, significantly improving and boosting its situational awareness. To do so, it is necessary for the vehicles to broadcast the V2V ids of their neighbors.

A. Graph Laplacian and LMS based solution

Before we proceed with the distributed implementation of (4), it is required to define the strongly convex $\mathcal{J}(\cdot)$. Laplacian framework of (5) facilitates the derivation of the desired risk function. To be more specific, consider the star graph in Fig. 3 of ego vehicle 3. The latter aims to estimate only the positions of its direct neighborhood, putting itself at the center of this topology, whereas the associated local Laplacian matrix $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| \times |\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$ is defined exactly as the extended Laplacian matrix of the original graph. By definition, star graph is a sparse topology, since only links between leafs and center do exist. Vehicles of $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$ transmit their noisy self position measurements to i , in order to the latter, together with its own self position, determines the local vector of anchors $\hat{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$. Apart from position measurements, neighboring vehicles transmit also the differentials corresponding to i , i.e., $\delta_{j \rightarrow i}^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{j \rightarrow i}^{(x,t)} & \delta_{j \rightarrow i}^{(y,t)} \end{bmatrix}^T$ with $\delta_{j \rightarrow i}^{(x,t)} = -\tilde{z}_{d,j,i}^{(t)} \sin \tilde{z}_{az,j,i}^{(t)}$ and $\delta_{j \rightarrow i}^{(y,t)} = -\tilde{z}_{d,j,i}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{az,j,i}^{(t)}$. Note that the previous step implies a data association pre-processing step between V2V ids and visually extracted measurements, which we assume that is given to us. By putting together all the differentials to vector $\hat{\delta}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_i^{(x,t)} & \left\{ \delta_{j \rightarrow i}^{(x,t)} \right\} & \delta_i^{(y,t)} & \left\{ \delta_{j \rightarrow i}^{(y,t)} \right\} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$, we define the local vector comprising of all the available measurements (self, relative, transmitted) to i : $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\delta}_i^{(t)T} & \hat{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(t)T} \end{bmatrix}^T$. In that way, $\mathcal{J}(\cdot)$ is given by:

$$\mathcal{J}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}; \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}) = \left\| \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} \right\|^2, \quad (8)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)} \end{bmatrix}$. Note that if $\lambda = 0$ then i simply minimizes $\mathcal{J}(\cdot)$ without considering the smoothness term of (4). This least-squares minimization approach was named **Graph Laplacian Awareness** or **GLA**. Finally, the two main steps of the proposed local diffusion scheme which address (4), based on [16] and LMS algorithm are given below:

$$\hat{\psi}_i^{(t,k+1)} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k)} - \mu_{2,i}^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)T} \left(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k)} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k+1)} = \mu_{2,i}^{(t)} \lambda \sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} \mathbf{a}_{il} \odot \hat{\psi}_i^{(t,k+1)}, \quad (10)$$

with $\mu_{2,i}^{(t)} > 0$ a small scalar step size and $\lambda = 1/\mu_{2,i}^{(t)}$. Note that [16] proves that the combination step (10) derives exactly from the smoothness term if we minimize (4) with respect to $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}$.

Therefore, vehicle i receives the relative observations and self positions from its neighbors, defines the Laplacian matrix of star topology and estimates the intermediate location vector following the adaptation equation (9). Afterwards, i receives the intermediate estimations from its neighbors, keeps and combines only the common and overlapping locations and discards the others. After K iterations, each vehicle is able to learn accurately enough the target location vector. The proposed scheme was named **GLA based on local diffusion LMS** or **GLA-LDL** and its main steps are summarized on **Algorithm 1**.

Algorithm 1: GLA-LDL

Input: Time horizon T , Number of iterations K
Output: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,K)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$

- 1 **for** $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ **do**
- 2 **for each ego vehicle i in parallel do**
- 3 Vehicles transmit to i their self positions and the corresponding differentials;
- 4 i defines matrix $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)}$ and vector $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}$;
- 5 Initialize $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,1)}$ minimizing $\mathcal{J}(\cdot)$ from (8);
- 6 **for** $k = 1, \dots, K$ **do**
- 7 $\hat{\psi}_i^{(t,k+1)} =$
- 8 $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k)} - \mu_{2,i}^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)T} \left(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k)} \right);$
- 9 $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t,k+1)} = \mu_{2,i}^{(t)} \lambda \sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} \mathbf{a}_{il} \odot \hat{\psi}_i^{(t,k+1)};$
- 10 **end**
- 11 **end**

B. Choice of combination weights

It can be inferred from the previous discussion that the core element of the proposed CA scheme is the choice of combination weights, so as to effectively fuse the overlapping estimations. Although (3) describes the general rule, it doesn't provide any closed form for the specific weights. In

the general framework of information diffusion on graphs, where the nodes of the graph estimate a single and entirely common across them parameter vector, the metropolis rule [18] is a popular and efficient choice for combination weights. However, it doesn't satisfy (3) in the case of local diffusion. Therefore, we provide below the modified metropolis rule, which determines the associated combination weight a_{il}^j for each overlapping index j of the parameter vectors of vehicles i and l :

$$a_{il}^j = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\max(|\mathcal{N}_{ij}^{(t)}|, |\mathcal{N}_{lj}^{(t)}|)}, & l \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)} \text{ and } l \neq i \\ 1 - \sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}_{ij}^{(t)} \setminus i} a_{il}^j, & i = l \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Note that (11) assigns a specific weight for each overlapping location estimated by vehicles i and l , instead of determining a single combination weight for the entire intermediate estimation of l as in (7).

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

A. Simulation setup

We carried out simulations to verify the performance of the proposed scheme using Python and CARLA simulator. A PC Laptop with 8GB RAM and Intel Core i7-1065G7 CPU @ 1.3 GHz was used. The trajectories of 150 vehicles, with simulation horizon $T = 448$ and time interval $dt = 0.4sec$ were extracted by CARLA. Velocities of vehicles range between 0 (e.g. waiting at traffic lights) and $74km/h$. A random ego vehicle along with the associated cluster is chosen for the evaluation, and its trajectory is shown in the heatmaps of Fig. 6. As far as the simulation parameters is concerned, $\sigma_d = 1m$, $\sigma_{az} = 4^\circ$, $\sigma_x = 3m$, $\sigma_y = 2.5m$ and $K = 30$. Apart from **GLA**, **GLA-LDL** and **GLLMS**, the global awareness algorithm of **GLLME** [9] was also used. The evaluation has been performed studying the impact of unknown multi-hop neighbors or *missing entries* (which affect global awareness), and the effect of vehicle connections, as dictated by communication range r_c , in the convergence speed and accuracy. Parameter r_c is much lower than typical $200m$ in order to reduce computational load. For evaluation metrics, we used the Location Awareness Error (LAE) as measured by vehicle i : $LAE_i^{(t)} = \sqrt{(1/|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|) \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} (LE_{j \leftarrow i}^{(t)})^2}$, where $LE_{j \leftarrow i}^{(t)}$ is the euclidean location error of j as measured by i , the Root Mean Square Error over time horizon of LAE: $RT-LAE_i$, and the averaged LAE over the iterations of each time instant: $ALAE_i^{(k)} = (1/T) \sum_{t=1}^T LAE_i^{(t,k)}$.

B. Evaluation study

1) *Impact of unknown multi-hop neighbors*: Proposed solution aims to overcome the limitation of global awareness in the case of lacking location information of multi-hop neighbors at the initialization stage. Parameter p indicates the rate of these vehicles whose position is unknown by the ego vehicle. Note that for **GLA-LDL** and **GLA** p is always equal to 100%. The results of this study with $p = 0, 10, 20\%$ are depicted in Fig. 4

Fig. 4. Convergence with different rates of unknown multi-hop neighbors

TABLE I
RT-LAE (m) VS NUMBER p OF UNKNOWN MULTI-HOP NEIGHBORS

p	GLA-LDL	GLA	GLLMS	GLLME	Noisy source
0%	2.1	2.9	2.2	2.16	3.91
10%	2.1	2.9	14.7	13.8	3.91
20%	2.1	2.9	22.16	22.16	3.91

and TABLE I with $r_c = 30m$. The size of cluster which ego vehicle belongs to ranges between 2 and 97 vehicles, while the size of its neighborhood is between 2 and 11. As Fig. 4-(a) shows, our solution succeeds in hitting $ALAE$ lower than $1.6m$ in less than 5 iterations, while **GLLME** surpasses $1.8m$ and remains stable after the 10th iteration. This behavior is also apparent in TABLE I, where **GLA-LDL** reduced $RT-LAE$ of standalone position source by **45%**, with respect to **24%** of **GLA**, **42%** of **GLLMS** and **43%** of **GLLME**. It also proves the benefits of combining the overlapping estimations of vehicles following (10), since the *without combination step* **GLA** is much less accurate. Increasing p to 10% and 20%, Fig. 4-(b),(c) prove that global awareness is totally unable to converge, significantly increasing $ALAE$ beyond $20m$. The proposed solution remains unaffected by this, since it was explicitly developed in order to counter this issue. Therefore, we conclude that as p increases, so does **GLLMS** and **GLLME** remove away from convergence, while **GLA-LDL** achieves a significant reduction of $RT-LAE$ in less than 5 iterations. We verify that defining a dynamic target location vector for each one of the vehicles instead of a common across them, it benefits CA ability in CAVs.

2) *Impact of connections*: In order to evaluate the convergence ability and location accuracy of our scheme in the case of dynamic and sparse communication topologies, we studied the effect of communication range r_c . The latter parameter indicates the amount of vehicles which comprise the specific cluster, as well as how dynamic the topology of connections is. With $r_c = 40m$ cluster's size ranges between 2 and 145, while neighborhood's size between 2 and 13. Varying

size of corresponding topologies, indicate dynamic connection links among vehicles. The results are summarized in Fig. 5 and TABLE II. We choose $p = 0\%$, thus **GLLMs** and

Fig. 5. Impact of neighbors' number and CARLA visualization

TABLE II
RT-LAE (m) VS COMMUNICATION RANGE r_c

r_c	$ \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)} $	GLA-LDL	GLA	<i>GLLMs</i>	<i>GLLME</i>	Noisy source
20m	2-9	2.22	2.76	2.11	2.07	3.74
30m	2-11	2.1	2.9	2.2	2.16	3.91
40m	2-13	1.89	2.93	1.86	1.82	3.81

GLLME performances can be considered biased, though very close to **GLA-LDL**. Increasing r_c , $RT - LAE$ of **GLA-LDL** reduces, reaching its minimum $1.89m$ at $r_c = 40m$, reducing by **50%** the error of noisy source. This performance should be correlated with the fact that $RT - LAE$ of **GLA** slightly increases as r_c increases, verifying that with the neighborhood's size growing larger, CA task seems to be more challenging. Fig. 5-(a) proves that considering larger amount of overlapping estimations through larger combination weights positively influences convergence speed. For example, $ALAE$ at 10th iteration is equal to $1.8, 1.6$ and $1.2m$, respectively for $r_c = 20, 30, 40m$. Therefore, we can conclude that the combination step of the proposed **GLA-LDL** provides the scalability to modifying topologies, facilitating the efficient integration of neighboring vehicles' estimations. The accuracy which ego vehicle estimates its neighbors' positions at time instant $t = 440$ and $r_c = 30m$ is shown in Fig. 5-(b). Instantaneous location error of ego vehicle is shown in the trajectory heatmaps of Fig. 6. Both **GLA** and **GLA-LDL**

Fig. 6. Heatmaps of $LE_{i←i}^{(t)}$

achieved almost the same accuracy, i.e., between 1 and $5m$. Multi-coloring is attributed to the Gaussian randomness of measurement errors. Evidently, local diffusion with respect to *without combination* **GLA** proves to be more beneficial in enhancing the awareness ability of vehicle.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper a local information diffusion based awareness scheme has been derived, which focuses on enhancing the situational awareness of CAVs. The distributed novel framework robustifies already developed global awareness solutions against *missing entries* or when all-to-all V2V connections aren't established. To do so, it makes use of the fact that neighboring vehicles share common target positions that need to be estimated and optimally combined. Collaborating multimodal sensor fusion has been performed within a linear approach, utilizing local Laplacian matrix, differential coordinates and LMS algorithm. High accuracy is reached within a very few number of iterations and exchange of estimations.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Arthurs, *et al.*, "A taxonomy and survey of edge cloud computing for intelligent transportation systems and connected vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, pp. 1–16, 2021.
- [2] M. A. Javed and E. B. Hamida, "Measuring safety awareness in cooperative ITS applications," in *2016 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference*. IEEE, 2016.
- [3] S. Kuutti, *et al.*, "A survey of the state-of-the-art localization techniques and their potentials for autonomous vehicle applications," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 829–846, 2018.
- [4] R. M. Buehrer, H. Wymeersch, and R. M. Vaghefi, "Collaborative sensor network localization: Algorithms and practical issues," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 106, no. 6, pp. 1089–1114, 2018.
- [5] S. Safavi, U. A. Khan, S. Kar, and J. M. F. Moura, "Distributed localization: A linear theory," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 106, no. 7, pp. 1204–1223, 2018.
- [6] Y. Fan, K. Ding, X. Qi, and L. Liu, "Cooperative localization of 3d mobile networks via relative distance and velocity measurement," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 25, no. 9, pp. 2899–2903, 2021.
- [7] P. Yang *et al.*, "Multi-sensor multi-vehicle (msmv) localization and mobility tracking for autonomous driving," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, no. 12, pp. 14 355–14 364, 2020.
- [8] T. Liang, *et al.*, "Uav aided positioning systems for ground devices: Fundamental limits and algorithms," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, pp. 1–1, 2022.
- [9] N. Piperigkos, A. S. Lalos, and K. Berberidis, "Graph laplacian diffusion localization of connected and automated vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, pp. 1–15, 2021.
- [10] T.-K. Chang, K. Chen, and A. Mehta, "Resilient and consistent multi-robot cooperative localization with covariance intersection," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 197–208, 2022.
- [11] N. Piperigkos, A. S. Lalos, and K. Berberidis, "Multi-modal cooperative awareness of connected and automated vehicles in smart cities," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Smart Internet of Things (SmartIoT)*, 2021, pp. 377–382.
- [12] A. Dosovitskiy *et al.*, "CARLA: An open urban driving simulator," in *Conference on Robot Learning*, 2017, pp. 1–16.
- [13] A. Kloukiniotis *et al.*, "Countering adversarial attacks on autonomous vehicles using denoising techniques: A review," *IEEE Open Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 3, pp. 61–80, 2022.
- [14] C. Chen, *et al.*, "Dynanet: Neural kalman dynamical model for motion estimation and prediction," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 32, no. 12, pp. 5479–5491, 2021.
- [15] J. Zhang and S. Singh, "Visual-lidar odometry and mapping: low-drift, robust, and fast," in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2015, pp. 2174–2181.
- [16] R. Nassif, S. Vlaski, C. Richard, and A. H. Sayed, "Learning over multitask graphs—part i: Stability analysis," *IEEE Open Journal of Signal Processing*, vol. 1, pp. 28–45, 2020.
- [17] R. Nassif, *et al.*, "Multitask learning over graphs: An approach for distributed, streaming machine learning," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 14–25, 2020.
- [18] S. Chouvardas, K. Slavakis, and S. Theodoridis, "Adaptive robust distributed learning in diffusion sensor networks," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 59, no. 10, pp. 4692–4707, 2011.